

HIGH MOLECULAR WEIGHT THERMOSETTING PHENOL-FORMALDEHYDE OLIGOMER: STUDY OF CURING CONDITIONS

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Abstract. This study investigates the synthesis of high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde oligomers and the conditions influencing their gelation and gel fraction yield. The results confirm the suitability of these oligomers for processing at 180–200°C and their potential applications in producing high-quality polymer products.

Keywords: high molecular weight oligomer, phenol-formaldehyde resins, thermosetting properties, gelation time, gel fraction, processing temperature, copolycondensation, co-oligomer.

Introduction. Traditional phenol-formaldehyde resins are characterized by various properties that are thermoplastic or thermosetting. They can initially be liquid or solid. Based on them, mixing with different polymers opens wide opportunities for the production of a material that combines the advantages of several polymers [1, 2, 3].

Research on the creation of this type of thermosetting oligomers usually includes the following most necessary steps: synthesis of monomers, synthesis of oligomers based on them, study of their physico-chemical properties and structure, study of the effect of synthesis conditions on their technological properties [4,5].

Phenol-formaldehyde oligomers provide durable and high-quality coatings used in various industries [6, 7]. Phenol-formaldehyde oligomers provide long-term protection against corrosion, scratches and cracks when used as a coating. Heat treated phenol-formaldehyde resin coatings have maximum chemical resistance even in highly acidic environments [8, 9]. Such materials are used as coatings for chimneys, pumps, pipes and tanks [10]. Therefore, one of the main technological properties of such composite materials is viscosity strength and thermosetting stability, which significantly depends on the degree of solidification (gel fraction).

Results and analysis. To do this, we synthesized our monomers phenolalcohol based on phenol and formaldehyde, diethyleneglycoladipinatol based on adipic acid and diethyleneglycol. The copolycondensation process of our two synthesized monomers, diethyleneglycoladipinitol and phenolalcohol,

in a ratio of 1:40 mol/mol, was carried out in the presence of a catalyst (30% solution of maleic anhydride) under conditions (pH=3). As a result, a high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde oligomer was synthesized.

We studied the technological properties of the synthesized high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde oligomer. The main focus is on studying the conditions for the transition (solidification) of oligomers to the fixed state. As a result of studying these conditions, the ability to obtain press compositions will improve and labor productivity will increase.

The gelation times of the synthesized (PhA:DEGA 40:1 mol/mol) high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde co-oligomer were performed according to GOST R 57779-2017 (ISO 8987:2005).

The gelation times of the synthesized co-oligomer at temperatures of 130°C, 150°C, 180°C, and 200°C were studied. The temperature dependence diagram of the gelation time of a high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde co-oligomer is presented in Figure 1.

1-Figure. Susceptibility to gellanization times of high molecular mass thermoresponsive phenol-formaldehyde co-oligomer at FS:DEGA ratio of 40:1 mol/mol

1-synthesis duration 20 minutes; 2-synthesis duration 60 minutes;
3-synthesis duration 90 minutes;

The gelation time decreases with increasing synthesis time. At 130°C, the gelation time is 1496 seconds 20 minutes after the start of synthesis, while after 90 minutes this indicator is reduced to 420 seconds. When the temperature was raised to 200°C, the gelation times were reduced to 156, 108, and 68 seconds.

Changing the synthesis conditions improved the thermoresponsive properties of the oligomer.

The diagram above shows that we observed that the gelation time increased with increasing synthesis time for our high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde co-oligomers. At the same time, we can see that the high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde co-oligomers we synthesized have a longer lifetime than traditional phenol-formaldehyde oligomers. This is because simple thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde oligomers in solid form (not in solution) partially gel after 20-30 days and become unusable [1].

While the gelatinization time of the thermosetting oligomers discussed above determines the time they remain in a liquid state at a given temperature, the degree of cross-linking is determined by the yield of the gel fraction during extraction. This technological property of thermosetting oligomers determines the processing time of a particular oligomer or a composition based on it under certain temperature conditions.

We also studied the gel fraction yield of a high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde co-oligomer synthesized at a 1:40 mol/mol ratio of DEGA:PhA. We conducted this study in accordance with GOST R 59112-2020 (ISO 10147:2011). The gel fraction was obtained by annealing the studied oligomer at temperatures of 150°C, 180°C, and 200°C for 10 min., 30 min., 1 h., 5 h., and 10 h. The solidified oligomers were placed in filter paper bags and

extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus. A mixture of ethyl alcohol-dimethylformamide in a 50:50 volume ratio was chosen as the extractant. The extracted products

were dried and the degree of solidification (gel fraction) was calculated based on the calculations. The result is presented in Figure 2 as a graph of the gel fraction yield versus processing temperature and time.

Figure 2 describes the gel fraction yield of a high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde co-oligomer synthesized at a DEGA:PhA ratio of 1:40 mol/mol. As can be seen from the data in Figure 2, in curve 1, when the sol-oligomer was treated at 150^oC for 10 minutes, the gel fraction yield was 3%, and when the curing time was increased to 30 minutes, the gel fraction yield increased sharply to 63%. Then, when the curing time was increased to 1, 5, and 10 hours, the gel fraction yield slowed to 78-86-90%, respectively.

Increasing the processing temperature to 180^oC (curve 2) and 200^oC (curve 3) resulted in a slight increase in the gel fraction yield from 4.5% to 6.4% at 10 minutes. Increasing the processing time to 30 minutes resulted in a sharp increase in the yield of the gel fraction to 77-83%. Thus, increasing the processing temperature and time leads to a gradual increase in the yield of the gel fraction. When the processing time was increased to 10 hours, the gel fraction yield was 93% at 180^oC (curve 2) and 95.5% at 200^oC (curve 3).

Usually, in the production of various types of plastics based on thermosetting oligomers, depending on the type of binders and the thermosetting oligomer, it is enough to achieve 70-80% productivity of gel fractions. The high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde co-oligomer we have achieved as a result of our scientific research allows for a gel fraction yield of >98% at processing temperatures, which ensures high production technological tests (thermal-physical, physical-mechanical, dielectric properties) of the resulting plastic products.

Therefore, all synthesized high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde co-oligomer products can be processed at temperatures of 180-200^oC under technologically acceptable conditions without reducing the productivity of processing equipment.

The conclusion. In conclusion, this study investigated the technological properties of high molecular weight thermosetting phenol-formaldehyde co-oligomers. It was found that the synthesized co-oligomers are more stable and have longer-term use compared to traditional phenol-formaldehyde resins. The effect of temperature and time on gelation time and gel fraction yield was studied. The results show that optimal processing conditions are provided at a temperature of 180–200^oC, at which the gel fraction yield exceeds 98%.

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